

SOCIAL SCIENCES

IMPACT OF IN-STORE ATMOSPHERE ON CONSUMER PURCHASE INTENTION: A STUDY ON KAZAKHSTANI UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN ISTANBUL

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of in-store atmospheric features on consumer purchase intention. The atmospheric features being examined were music, scent, temperature, lighting, colour, display and layout, and cleanliness. The data was collected using a structured questionnaire and the sample population was Kazakhstani university students in Istanbul. The findings suggest that several atmospheric variables of the store, such as, music, scent, temperature, display and layout, and lighting impacts the purchase intention of customers during in-store shopping.

Keywords: *In-Store Shopping, Purchase Intention, Atmosphere, Cleanliness, Scent, Lighting, Music, Colour, Display and Layout, Temperature.*

1. Introduction

With the introduction of e-commerce platforms, many people now engage in online shopping rather than visiting physical stores. However, this shift from physical to online shopping does not stop vast number of people from visiting traditional physical stores for shopping. For this reason, several other studies suggest that in-store features like interior and exterior design, music, lighting and staff, play an important role in shaping customer impression and decisions [1]. Due to this, now retail businesses try to focus on these features of the stores and thus, positively influence customers' purchasing intentions with right store colour, correct set up of atmosphere, music, internal fittings, visuals and even window displays [2].

Several other studies found that mentioned in-store features are very important in attracting customers, increasing consumer retention and building brand positioning [3]. As all these features affect the shopping time and sale/purchase evaluation significantly [4]. However, when it comes to in-store atmosphere, only very limited number of studies have researched this matter, especially among international student population of Istanbul, thus, this study aims in examining if atmospheric variables of the stores impact the purchase intention of customers. Just as, the role of in-store atmosphere on success of the business cannot be denied [5].

2. Literature Review

2.1 Purchase Intention

Purchase intention is the possibility of the customer to purchase the product [6]. In other words, purchase intention is the customer's attempt and effort to buy the product [7]. Based on the definition, purchase intention is the probability and willingness of the consumer to buy the product or service from the business. However, the purchase intention arises when customer enters the store and initiates buying interest from his or her side, therefore, as the buying interest increases so

does the desire and intention of the customer to try, buy and own the product or service [8].

2.2 In-Store Atmospheric Variables

One of the first definitions of store atmospherics was given by Kotler in 1973 as "buying environments [designed] to produce specific emotional effects in the buyer that enhance his purchase probability" [9]. In relation, in the context of services marketing, this term is often replaced with the term "servicescape" which is defined as "all of the objective physical factors that can be controlled by the firm to enhance (or constrain) employee and customer actions" by Bitner in 1992 [10]. Thus, the store atmospheric variables used in this study are all taken from the servicescape model first introduced by Bitner and some of the main variables from environmental dimensions of the model are examined in this study. One of these variables is music, hence, a study done by Smith suggests that up-beat music triggers impulse buying in customers [11].

Not just this, another study found that pleasant music increases the customer purchase intention, increases sales and customer consumption time [12]. On the other hand, cleanliness increases the duration customers stay in the store, which in return affects sales positively [13]. Another very important variable is scent, and it is found that pleasant scents in the store increase the customer's journey in the store, creates good impression and eventually leads to increased buying interest [14,15]. While on the other hand, extreme temperatures result in negative word of mouth among customers, as customers spend less time in the store and eventually leave dissatisfied [16].

Interestingly, several studies found the importance of lighting as well. Based on the results of some of these studies, good lighting increases customer excitement and positively impacts their purchasing behaviour [17]. In addition, another study conducted by Yoo, Park, & MacInnis in 1998 also found that apart from all the above-mentioned dimensions, display and colours in

the store create positive perception in customers and increases their time in the store [18]. Not just this, it was even found that design and display of products contribute to one fourth of all the sales in a business and increases purchase intention [19,20]. Same was found in the study by Huddleston, that product display boosts sales and customer shopping experience[21], while Krasonikolakis found that store layout has a major impact on customer shopping experience both digitally and in traditional shopping [22].

3. Research Design & Methodology

This research is a quantitative research, thus primary data was collected through structured questionnaire and snowball sampling method was utilized. The sample population for this study was Kazakhstani university students studying in Istanbul. In addition, the data was analysed on SPSS statistical package. Firstly, confirmatory factor analysis was done to assess the validity of the scale items used in the survey, afterwards, the reliability was checked through Cronbach's alpha. In total our study included 8 scales consisting of music, scent, temperature, lighting, colour, display and layout, cleanliness, and purchase intention.

Furthermore, all the analyses indicated that all the scales were highly reliable and valid. Therefore, the next step was multiple linear regression through which the impact of each independent variable of atmospheric dimensions was measured on the dependent variable of purchase intention. The needed sample size for this research was 369, nevertheless, to have more generalisable results with more statistical power and mitigated effect of any potential errors, 375 surveys were administered to students, out of which 372 were valid for analysis. The original items of the questionnaire were developed by Han, Kuang, Low & Yap [23] and Vijay [24], however, this study utilized the modified version of the questionnaire with higher reliability and validity,

modified version of the questionnaire was developed by Hussain and Ali [25]. The questionnaire consisted of 40 questions in total, with 34 questions being scale items and 6 questions being general and introductory questions.

The introductory and general questions included respondents' age, level of education, gender, frequency of shopping, types of shopping and the main question asking the respondent to think about one of the retail stores they visited last time and answer all the questions while keeping in mind this visit. This approach ensured that respondents focus on a specific store and thus, develop accurate results for the study. Hence, the findings inferred to support and rejection of several hypotheses of the study. Thereby, the research model, objective and hypotheses were as follows:

Research Objective:

The main objective of this research is to find out whether atmospheric variables/features impact the purchase intention of customers during their time in a retail store.

Hypotheses:

H1: Music has significant impact on purchase intention of consumers.

H2: Cleanliness has significant impact on purchase intention of consumers.

H3: Temperature has significant impact on purchase intention of consumers.

H4: Scent has significant impact on purchase intention of consumers.

H5: Lighting has significant impact on purchase intention of consumers.

H6: Display and Layout have significant impact on purchase intention of consumers.

H7: Colour has significant impact on purchase intention of consumers.

Figure. 1 Conceptual Model of Research

4. Results

Shortly, the results of the hypothesis testing based on multiple linear regression led to the support of H1, H3, H4, H5 and H6 with the p value being <0.05. Therefore, the 5 hypotheses of the study were supported, meaning that there is impact of music, temperature, scent, lighting, display and layout on consumer purchase intention during instore shopping. However,

H2 and H7 due to $p > 0.05$, were rejected, meaning cleanliness and colour has insignificant or no impact on consumer purchase intention during in-store shopping. The supported hypotheses align with the findings of the studies done by Smith [11], Holbrook and Anand [12], in which the impact of music on purchase intention was also found. Moreover, regarding our fourth supported hypothesis, Banat and Wandebori [14] as well as Yalch

and Spangenberg [15] also found the impact of scent on purchase behaviour of consumers. While on the other hand, same as in findings of Lam [16] and Mehrabian [17] this study also found that temperature and lighting also have an impact on consumer purchasing behaviour.

Lastly, this study also corresponds with the findings of the studies of Mills et al. [19], Ward et al. [20], Huddleston et al. [21] and Krasonikolakis [22] in which the impact of display and layout of the store was found to have an impact on consumer buying behaviour. However, H2 and H7 contradict the findings of Gajanayake et al. [13] and Yoo et al. [18] in which the impact of cleanliness and colour on customer purchase intention was found, while in this study, this impact was not discovered.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of this research, it becomes evident that during in-store shopping consumers' purchase behaviour, predominantly purchase intention is affected by several atmospheric variables of the store, such as, music, scent, temperature, display and layout, and lighting. However, colour and cleanliness were found to have no impact on consumer purchase intention during in-store shopping. Hence, with these findings, it is advisable for businesses and business managers to enhance the atmospheric features that were found to impact consumer purchase intention, to further increase their sales, boost consumer base and result in efficient business progress.

Besides, for future research, it is advised to do this research on a larger population, in order to get more statistically strong and generalisable results. Furthermore, different data collection techniques could be implemented and sample population could be more diverse which will in return lead to more accuracy, reliability, and external validity of the research results as well as better representation of diversity, which is very important in fields like marketing and consumer behaviour. However, due to the limited number of studies focusing on this case especially among international university students studying in Istanbul, findings of this research contributed to current literature. As, previous studies were done mostly outside of this region and not on student population, especially Kazakhstani students in Istanbul. Thereby, findings of this research also filled several gaps in the research.

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